

5th ISAJ Symposium on *Advances in Natural Sciences & Technologies*

December 1, 2014
Auditorium, Embassy of India, Tokyo, Japan

Organized by
Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Honorary Patron:
H.E. Ms. Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa
The Ambassador of India

Honorary Advisor:
Dr. Chadaram Sivaji
S & T Counsellor, Indian Embassy

Convener: Dr. Sunil Kaul
Co-convener: Dr. Neeraj Kumar

Organizing Committee:

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About ISAJ (*website: isaj.org*)

With the progresses in India and Japan bilateral cooperation in Science and Technology, there have been growing opportunities lately for Indian researchers to work in Japanese scientific and technological research organizations and universities. In this rapidly changing scenario, we felt the need of forming an association such as the Indian Scientist Association in Japan (ISAJ: pronounced as Ai-Saj), which would provide an organizational framework to promote greater interaction between Indian researchers based in Japan, as well as Indian and Japanese researchers, for the development and strengthening of research networks. At the same time, to provide an information portal for the advantage of Indian researchers on science and technology news, events, funding opportunities, and every nuance of research system in Japan. Besides the Indian researchers' community can share their experiences about culture and way of life in Japan through this forum for the advantage of potential researchers in India who are planning to pursue their academic/research career in Japan. This would also provide avenues for the Indian researchers to flash their academic profile and research achievements through the ISAJ portal for wider awareness of the expertise in their respective field of research. Periodically, ISAJ will bestow awards and honors on the Indian and Japanese scientists in recognition of contribution made to the advancement of our knowledge through their pioneering Japan-India collaborative research work. Occasionally, ISAJ will also hold meetings, symposia, conference to disseminate information about the research activities carried out by the Indian researchers based

in Japan and to promote communication among Japanese and Indian researchers that would benefit India–Japan S&T collaboration. ISAJ would also help to build a bridge between Japanese and Indian research organizations to undertake collaborative research projects mutually beneficial to both the countries.

Organizational Structure

ISAJ is registered as a Japanese non-profit organization (NPO) under Japan's NPO law. Tsukuba has been decided to be ISAJ's headquarter. The Executive Body is ISAJ's governing body and is responsible for directing the affairs and determining the future of the Society. The Executive Body will appoint some of the Executive Body members to take responsibilities such as the Chapter Presidents of six different regions in Japan (Hokkaido, Tohoku, Tokyo, Tsukuba, Fukuoka, and Osaka). Election for the Office bearers (Chairman, Vice–Chairman, Secretary, and Assistant Secretary, Chief–Editor, Associate–Editor, and Treasurer) will be held biennially and all the members of the society can take part in election process.

Honorary Patron:

H. E. Ms. Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa, Ambassador, Embassy of India, Japan

Honorary Adviser:

Dr. Chadaram Sivaji, Counsellor (Science & Technology), Embassy of India, Japan

Executive Body:

Dr. Sunil Kaul, AIST, Tsukuba (Chairman)

Dr. Alok Singh, NIMS, Tsukuba (Vice–Chairman)

Dr. Kedar Mahapatra, Tokai University, Shizuoka (General Secretary)

Dr. Swadhin Behera, JAMSTEC, Yokohama (Chief Editor)

Dr. Samik Ghosh, Systems Biology Institute, Tokyo (Treasurer)

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Sponsors

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小宮葉子記念会

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डा. आर. चिदम्बरम्

भारत सरकार के प्रमुख वैज्ञानिक सलाहकार
एवम्

डी.ए.इ. - होमी भाभा प्रोफेसर

Dr. R. Chidambaram

Principal Scientific Adviser to the Govt. of India
&

DAE - Homi Bhabha Professor

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Message

I am very happy that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan is organizing the 5th ISAJ Symposium on 1st December, 2014 and that the theme for this year is 'Advances in Natural Sciences and Technology'. It is also a matter of great pleasure that our Embassy is the venue of the Meeting and is taking a deep interest in scientific collaboration with Japan.

Most frontier topics in science and technology today are multi-disciplinary. Health Care is an important social issue; materials are at the centre of every technology; mitigation and adaptation to climate change threat is a challenge; and energy efficiency is so important and, in the Indian National Action Plan for Climate Change, there is a special mission on enhanced energy efficiency. All these topics will be part of the themes of the 5th ISAJ Symposium.

I congratulate ISAJ for its efforts to increase the scientific cooperation between India and Japan, including through organizing the Annual ISAJ Symposia, which give an opportunity for young scientists to interact with established and leading workers in various fields.

I wish the Symposium all success.

R Chidambaram

(R. Chidambaram)

17th November, 2014

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AMBASSADOR OF INDIA

भारत का राजदूत

MESSAGE

I am very happy to learn that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is organising its 5th annual Symposium at the Indian Embassy auditorium on December 01, 2014.

My Embassy is happy to associate itself with ISAJ in all its endeavours and for this annual event, where senior Japanese and Indian researchers share a common platform to promote cooperation and scientific collaboration and young researchers present and discuss their latest research. This year's theme aptly titled –*Advances in Natural Sciences and Technologies* – will help exchange on views on emanating technologies that will only grow and improve with time to make the world a better place to live in.

While thanking the members of the ISAJ and the participants in the symposium I hope for this symposium to act as a bridge between our scientific communities to collaborate further in the field of science and technology for the betterment of our two nations.

With my best wishes,

(Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa)

Tokyo

November 13, 2014

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Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Convener's Welcome

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we take this opportunity to welcome all the delegates to the 5th symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ). This year, the focus is on *Advances in Natural Sciences and Technologies*.

ISAJ is now a 6-year old Non Profit Organization (NPO). Conceived at the end of 2008 by coming together of many Indian researchers working in Japan, it was formally inaugurated by Prof. R. Chidambaram, Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India in January 2009, in the presence of His Excellency the then Ambassador of India. The main aim of ISAJ has been networking among Indian researchers for professional advancement and life in Japan. ISAJ has six chapters in Japan covering from Hokkaido to Osaka and we have been trying to promote regular seminars, free discussions and networking at the chapter level.

We have been meeting once a year in this auditorium by organizing an Annual Symposium, and today it is the fifth in the series. In this symposium we share our scientific research conducted in Japan, and listen to some prominent speakers from various fields of science. Some of the highlights of the past five years include (i) we make this event an interdisciplinary to allow wide participation and interactions. We believe that this is a unique opportunity and platform to learn beyond our specialized boundaries and get motivated to generate new research projects. We have had plenary sessions dealing with life sciences, material sciences, earth sciences and environmental sciences all together in all the past symposia with the invited talks by renowned scientists in each of these fields, (ii) every year Embassy of India has offered their generous support such as providing the venue, extending assistance in inviting special guests and including the fourth Annual ISAJ symposium held in 2012, as one of the activities in connection with the 60 years of diplomatic relations between India and Japan, (iii) every year, we organize a well-attended poster session and present the best poster awards to encourage the students and young researchers.

This year we have 3 Plenary Lectures, 8 Invited Lectures and 29 Contributed Abstracts. In addition, to encourage the students/young researchers, this year we have added Students and Young PI Sessions organized by students and young PIs, respectively.

Today, we are delighted to have been joined by several prominent scientists and we believe that it is a great opportunity for networking and also for building foundations for future scientific research collaborations to promote Science and Technology relationships.

We duly acknowledge the generous support of the Embassy of India, particularly Dr. Chadaram Sivaji, Counsellor, Science & Technology. We are extremely grateful to our sponsors, Komiya Yoko Memorial Association, Saint Gobain Corporation, Ambika Trading Co. and Bank of India for their generous support for this event. Finally, we take this opportunity to thank everyone for overwhelming support, to make this event happen.

We sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium, become aware of each others' scientific contributions, make friendships and scientific collaborations. We hope this will also inspire India-Japan collaborations and friendships along with developing stronger ties in Science and Technology.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Symposium Convener & Chairman, ISAJ

Neeraj Kumar
Symposium Co-convener

PROGRAM

December 1, 2014 (Monday)		
8:30 - 9:00	Registration	
9:00 - 9:05	Lighting of the lamp	
9:05 - 9:55	Inaugural Session	
9:05 - 9:10	Welcome Address	Sunil Kaul Chairman, ISAJ
9:10 - 9:20	Inaugural Address	H.E. Ms. Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa The Ambassador of India to Japan
9:20 - 9:40	Keynote	Noboru Yumoto Vice-President & Director General, Life Science, AIST
9:40 - 9:50	Address	Chadaram Sivaji Counselor Science & Technology, Embassy of India
9:50 - 9:55	Vote of Thanks	Alok Singh Vice Chairman, ISAJ
9:55 - 10:00	GROUP PHOTO	
10:00 - 10:15	COFFEE BREAK	
10:15 - 11:20	Plenary Session 1: Bio-imaging Chairs: Yoshihiro Ohmiya & D Sakthi Kumar	
10:15 - 10:35	Masataka Kinjo <i>Hokkaido University</i>	Study of Transcription Factor Using Fluorescence Cross-correlation Spectroscopy in the Living Cell
10:35 - 10:50	Toshimasa Uemura <i>AIST</i>	Long Term Labeling of Stem Cells by Internalizing Quantum Dots Using Mortalin Antibody –Application to Cartilage Regeneration, Study of Cancer Cells/Stem Cells Interaction antibody
10:50 - 11:05	Srivani Veerananarayanan <i>Toyo University</i>	Molecular Imaging with Nanoparticles: Big Tasks for Dwarf Players
11:05 - 11:20	Motomichi Doi <i>AIST</i>	Direct Visualization of Neuronal Circuit Formation, Function and Maintenance by Fluorescent-fusion Proteins in Living <i>C. elegans</i>
11:20 - 12:50	LUNCH & POSTER SESSION Chair: Neeraj Kumar	

12:50 - 13:55	Plenary Session 2: Earth Sciences	
	Chairs: Yukio Masumoto & Swadhin Behera	
12:50 - 13:10	Yukio Masumoto <i>Tokyo University</i>	EIOURI and IIOE-2: Two International Research Activities of Indian Ocean Oceanography
13:10 - 13:25	Prabir Patra <i>JAMSTEC</i>	Estimation of Hydroxyl Concentration in Earth's Atmosphere
13:25 - 13:40	Satsuki Matsumura <i>FRA</i>	Biological Oceanography from Space: Practical Application for Fisheries Management in a Changing Climate
13:40 - 13:55	J. V Ratnam <i>JAMSTEC</i>	Remote Effects of the North Indian Ocean Tropical Disturbances
13:55 - 14:10	COFFEE BREAK	
14:10 - 15:25	Plenary Session 3: Materials Science	
	Chairs: Yoko Yamabe-Mitarai & Alok Singh	
14:10 - 14:30	Yoko Yamabe-Mitarai <i>NIMS</i>	High Temperature Functional and Structure Ti Alloys
14:30 - 14:50	Isao H. Inoue <i>AIST</i>	Crisis of Transistor, and Beyond
14:50 - 15:10	Kazuya Shimoda <i>NIMS</i>	Recent Progress of SiC Ceramic Matrix Composites for Energy/Environmental Applications
15:10 - 15:25	Mukesh Kumar <i>NIMS</i>	Atomistic Modelling to Understand, Describe, and Design Absorber Materials for Thin-film Solar Cell Applications
15:25 - 15:40	COFFEE BREAK	
15:40 - 16:10	Session 4: Student Session	
	Chairs: Mahendra Kumar Pal & Anupama Choudhary	
	Jay Prakash, <i>Banaras Hindu University</i> Swapnil Ghodke, <i>Nagoya University</i> Xin Ji, <i>NIMS</i> Nupur Nigam, <i>Tsukuba University</i>	

16:10-16:50	Session 5: Young PI Session Chairs: Manish Biyani	
16:10 - 16:20	Mahesh K. Kaushik <i>Tsukuba University</i>	Prostaglandin D2 is Crucial for Seizure Suppression and Postictal Sleep
16:20 - 16:30	P. K. Hashim <i>Tokyo University</i>	Molecularly Engineered Bionanocaplets for Intracellular Delivery: Precise Size Control via Template Polymerization
16:30 - 16:40	Babita Shashni <i>Tsukuba University</i>	Implications of Targeting Transcriptional Factor PPAR Gamma for Breast Cancer Therapeutics
16:40-16:50	Bhupendra Sharma <i>Ritsumeikan University</i>	Development of a Novel Powder Metallurgy Route to Fabricate Biomedical Beta-Titanium Alloys
16:50 - 17:00	Concluding Session and Award Ceremony	

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I1 - Plenary

STUDY OF TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR USING FLUORESCENCE CROSS-CORRELATION SPECTROSCOPY IN THE LIVING CELL

Masataka Kinjo*

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Two-laser-beam fluorescence cross-correlation spectroscopy (FCCS) is promising technique that provides quantitative information about the interactions of biomolecules. By using FCCS, we determined the dissociation constant (K_d) of the p50/p65 heterodimer, homodimer of that, and also homodimer of glucocorticoid receptor (GR) in living cells. GR is a well-known steroid-dependent nuclear receptor protein. The classical view is unliganded GR resides in the cytoplasm, translocates to the nucleus upon ligand binding, and then associates with a specific position, namely glucocorticoid response elements (GRE), where GR act as a transcription factor. On the other hand, it is still a puzzle whether GR forms a dimer in the cytoplasm or in the nucleus before DNA binding or after that. Our result using FCCS suggested that high values of K_d in nucleus and so the dimer-monomer equivalent state in the nucleus and also cytoplasm. These findings support the existence of a “dynamic monomer pathway” and regulation of GR function can be controlled by concentration and balance of monomer and dimer ratio.

LONG TERM LABELING OF STEM CELLS BY INTERNALIZING QUANTUM DOTS USING MORTALIN ANTIBODY –APPLICATION TO CARTILAGE REGENERATION, STUDY OF CANCER CELLS/STEM CELLS INTERACTION

Toshimasa Uemura*¹, Mika Pietilae¹, Tomokazu Yoshioka², Ryuya Murai¹, Hanhsiu Hsu¹, Yui Onomura¹, Pi-chao Wang², Sunil Kaul¹, and Renu Wadhwa¹

¹*National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST),*

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Quantum dots (QD) are favorable nanoparticle for bioimaging for long term tracking of the implanted cells in tissue engineering. We have developed a novel labeling method for internalizing QDs to mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) using mortalin antibody [1]. The chondrocytes derived from QD labeled MSCs were implanted into rabbit osteochondral defects in total knee joint and successfully tracked for 6 months for evaluating the contribution of implanted cells [2]. Cartilage regeneration: at 8 weeks, the cells retained their morphology and the extracellular matrices were strongly stained by safranin-O, suggesting the active production of GAG. QD signal was observed throughout the regenerated tissue in the cartilage layer. Signal was still observed at 26 weeks after transplantation. Recently the interaction between cancer cells and MSCs have attracted much attention in basic scientists and clinicians. Interestingly we detected the intercellular transfer of QDs from hMSCs to MDA-MB-231 cells [3]. Moreover, the intercellular transfer of QDs was induced in hanging drop co-culture system. Fluorescent and electron microscope analysis revealed that the direct cell-to-cell interactions may be needed for the intercellular transfer of QD from hMSCs to MDA-MB-231. This is the first time when it was showed that the heterocellular cross talk between stromal cells and cancer cells may also include direct transfer of anti-apoptotic and pro-tumoral factors from stromal cells to cancer cells. Moreover, labeling of iPSc and embryonic kidney cells will be presented.

References

- [1] Ohyabu *et al.* Human Gene Ther., 20: 217-24 (2009)
- [2] Yoshikawa *et al.* J. Tissue Eng. Regen. Med., 5: 437-43 (2011)
- [3] Pietilae *et al.* Exp. Cell Res., 5: 437-43 (2013)

MOLECULAR IMAGING WITH NANOPARTICLES: BIG TASKS FOR DWARF PLAYERS

Srivani Veerananarayanan*, Aby Cheruvathoor Poullose, M. Sheikh Mohamed,
Sivakumar Balasubramanian, Aswathy Ravindran Girija, Toru Maekawa, and D. Sakthi Kumar[§]

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The prompt progression of imaging technology over the preceding period has unlocked prospect for the design of precise and functional probes for molecular imaging. While considerable effort of this technology at present rests at a proof-of-principle phase, the potential to detect and inspect transformed physiological states in humans is exceptionally appealing. Nanotechnology has been a chief advantage in this field because of the many diverse prospects for functionalizing nanoparticles as beacons for imaging. The present imaging modalities such as optical (Luminescent/Fluorescent), MRI (magnetic resonance imaging), PAT (photo acoustic imaging), CT (computed tomography), with the help of nanotechnology, assures to overcome the specific restraints of sensitivity and resolution, though, is in its infancy. The challenge will be to design relatively modest materials that can satiate the laborious demands with regard to safety and supportive in the analysis and treatment of human disease. In this presentation, the advancement in the field of nano-mediated molecular imaging would be highlighted with an emphasis on in-house development of such molecular imaging nanoprobe at Bio-Nano Electronics Research Centre. We are particularly interested in developing nanoprobe for cancer early detection and image guided therapy. A variety of nanoprobe have been prepared, evaluated and applied in various imaging modalities including: fluorescence, MRI, CT and photoacoustic imaging. The nanoparticles prepared in-house include near-infrared fluorescence (NIRF) quantum dots, iron oxide nanoparticles, core-shell metal-QD hybrids, metal sulfide/telluride nanocrystals etc.

**DIRECT VISUALIZATION OF NEURONAL CIRCUIT FORMATION,
FUNCTION AND MAINTENANCE BY FLUORESCENT-FUSION
PROTEINS IN LIVING *C. ELEGANS***

Motomichi Doi*

*Molecular Neurobiology Research Group and DAILAB, Biomedical Research Institute, AIST &
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To understand how a neuronal circuit in the brain is formed, what mechanism regulates its function, and how matured circuits are maintained, direct observation of both protein and cellular dynamics is one of the indispensable approaches. We are using *C. elegans*, a tiny soil worm, as a model system and are developing several visualization techniques for the neuronal analyses in living animals. *C. elegans* contains only 302 neurons but shows several higher neural functions such as learning and memory. Furthermore, its transparent body is quite suitable for imaging analyses of neuronal morphology and activity in vivo. By generating several fluorescent-fusion proteins which visualize circuit formation and function in living *C. elegans*, we are trying to elucidate the precise molecular and cellular mechanisms regulating both the brain functions and animal behaviors. In addition, we have also developed novel model animals which enable us to observe the protein dynamics causing neurodegenerative diseases. As a first step, we focused on the human amyloid-beta peptide which is considered as a primary factor of Alzheimer diseases. By arranging the linker sequences between amyloid-beta and fluorescent proteins, the aggregation states of amyloid-beta can be successfully monitored in living animals. In this presentation, we will discuss about the ongoing results of genetic and chemical screening to identify the components against amyloid-beta aggregation and toxicity. These visualization methods can be quite useful for understanding cellular mechanisms of neuronal maintenance and also for screening therapeutic factors for neurodegenerative diseases.

I5 - Plenary

EIOURI AND IIOE-2: TWO INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH ACTIVITIES OF INDIAN OCEAN OCEANOGRAPHY

Yukio Masumoto*

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The first coordinated investigation of the Indian Ocean was carried out during the International Indian Ocean Expedition (IIOE) in 1962–65, which was led by the Scientific Committee on Ocean Research (SCOR) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC). It consisted of a basin-wide survey that subsequently resulted in a comprehensive hydrographic atlas and number of regional studies. In the 50 years since the IIOE, many subsequent programs have contributed to our better understanding of the oceanic and atmospheric conditions, with new observational equipment and ocean modeling capability. Science foci have also been changed from understanding of climatological states to their variability during that period. Now, a second multi-disciplinary, multi-national Indian Ocean Expedition (IIOE-2), to be carried out over 2015-2020, is under its planning stage. One of the major components of IIOE-2 is an international effort to understand upwelling systems in the eastern Indian Ocean from physical, biogeochemical, and ecological viewpoints, which is named Eastern Indian Ocean Upwelling Research Initiative (EIOURI). This presentation introduces briefly these two initiatives in the Indian Ocean, which tackle new scientific challenges and are expected to provide new views of the Indian Ocean variability.

ESTIMATION OF HYDROXYL CONCENTRATION IN EARTH'S ATMOSPHERE

P. K. Patra^{*}, M. C. Krol, S. A. Montzka, T. Arnold, E. L. Atlas, B. R. Lintner, B. B. Stephens, B. Xiang, J. W. Elkins, P. J. Fraser, A. Ghosh, E. J. Hints, D. F. Hurst, K. Ishijima, P. B. Krummel, B. R. Miller, K. Miyazaki, F. L. Moore, J. Muhle, S. O'Doherty, R. G. Prinn, L. P. Steele, M. Takigawa, H. J. Wang, R. F. Weiss, S. C. Wofsy, and D. Young

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The hydroxyl radical (OH) is a key oxidant involved in the removal of air pollutants and greenhouse gases from the atmosphere. Because of its very short lifetime (~ 1 s), OH manifests high spatiotemporal variability. Since OH concentrations are also typically very low ($\sim 10^6$ molecules cm^{-3}), in situ measurements are challenging, and large differences between observations have prevented a direct validation of model-simulated OH distributions or an evaluation of uncertainties in the chemical mechanisms responsible for OH recycling under different environmental conditions. The global mean OH concentrations and its relative abundance in the northern and southern hemispheres remained poorly understood even today, as simulated by state-of-the-art atmospheric chemistry-transport model (ACTMs). Firstly an optimized set of methyl chloroform (CH_3CCl_3) emissions for the period of 1980 to 2013 are prepared using monthly varying OH fields. Two model OH fields used in this study are scaled to obtain 5 years of lifetime for CH_3CCl_3 for the decade of 2000s and successfully simulate the growth and decay of CH_3CCl_3 concentration in the atmosphere. (A lower amount of OH would fail to simulate the CH_3CCl_3 concentration decay rate during 2000s, and higher amount of OH lead to greater than observed seasonal cycle amplitude). After estimating the global mean OH concentration, using the JAMSTEC's ACTM simulations, we find that the amount of OH in both the hemispheres should be close to equal.

References:

[1] Nature, 513, 219ff, 11 September, (2014).

**BIOLOGICAL OCEANOGRAPHY FROM SPACE: PRACTICAL
APPLICATION FOR FISHERIES MANAGEMENT
IN A CHANGING CLIMATE**

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Phytoplankton biomass distribution can be detected by ocean color satellite observation. Since Nimbus-7 CZCS (coastal zone color scanner) was launched by NASA on 1978, ocean color data have been collected for monitoring large-scale and mesoscale distribution of biomass change. Phytoplankton biomass plays a major role in the global cycle of carbon dioxide and food chain in the ocean. Fishing activity and fisheries management in view of recent changes in the distribution and productivity of a number of fish species can be ascribed to regional climate variability and change in distribution of phytoplankton biomass. Satellite information such as sea surface temperature (SST) has been widely used to delineate Potential Fishing Zone (PFZ). Combined use of satellite derived SST, ocean color and sea surface topography could provide useful information to make PFZ map more useful for fishermen by especially saving time for fishing ground survey. On the other hand, the issue of overfishing poses a serious threat to many fish stocks and biological diversity. Since fish has been an important source of food for humans from ancient times, new approaches to sustainable fisheries management embracing conservation and environmental considerations are urgently needed. Bottom-up influences from primary productivity has been found difficult for estimating allowable biological catch (ABC) because of the inherent complexity of food webs. Top-down approach such as PPR (Primary Production Required) is found to be relatively effective. From an ecosystem-based management perspective, PPR provides an estimation of the ecosystem's carrying capacity based on its actual exploitation, and therefore represents a potential guideline for the future.

REMOTE EFFECTS OF THE NORTH INDIAN OCEAN TROPICAL DISTURBANCES

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Remote effects due to the tropical disturbances in the north Indian Ocean are investigated by analyzing long lasting (≥ 5 days) tropical disturbances, which reached at least the strength of tropical storms. The analysis is carried out for both the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon periods. The spatial and temporal distribution of the Outgoing Long wave Radiation (OLR) during the pre-monsoon disturbances over the Bay of Bengal reveals several interesting features. Temporal distribution of the OLR anomalies shows that the intraseasonal oscillations play an important role in the formation of those disturbances. The spatial distribution of the OLR anomalies shows a dipole with negative OLR anomalies over the Bay and positive OLR anomalies over the Indonesian region. The atmospheric response to the negative OLR anomalies results in positive temperature anomalies over the northwest India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Iran and Saudi Arabia, remote from the disturbance and the response to the positive anomalies causes slight increase in the sea surface temperature of the Arabian Sea. Negative OLR anomalies are also seen over the western Japan, due to the Rossby waves generated by the heating over the Bay of Bengal besides the enhancement of the so-called “Pacific-Japan” teleconnection pattern. However, the remote effects are not seen in the disturbances formed in the post- monsoon period. These results are important for enhancing the short and medium range forecasts.

I9 - Plenary

HIGH TEMPERATURE FUNCTIONAL AND STRUCTURE Ti ALLOYS

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Ti alloys are used as functional and structural materials due to their excellent corrosion resistance and high specific strength in different application fields such as medical, chemical, marine, and aerospace. We are trying to extract the excellent properties of Ti alloys, especially as high temperature materials. Generally, Ti alloys are classifiable in three groups by constituent phase; that is, hcp- α phase alloys, bcc- β phase alloys, and near- α alloys including small amount of β phase. The near α alloys are mainly used for high temperature application due to their higher strength than β alloys at high temperature. High-temperature Ti alloys are mainly used in the intermediate temperature range between 200 and 600 °C as blades, disks, vane, and case of fan in the compressor of jet engine. However, it is known that Ti alloys deteriorate by severe oxidation at the temperature above 600 °C. Then, in this talk, microstructure, phase transformation, mechanical properties, and oxidation behavior of Ti alloys are introduced. Another interesting application of Ti alloys is shape memory alloy. TiNi is widely used as shape memory alloys in medical, industrial, and home electronics. Recently, high temperature shape memory alloys (HTSMAs) have been expected for use in high temperature environment such as chemical plant and power plant et al. However, martensitic transformation temperature that strongly related with shape memory effect of TiNi is below 100 °C. Rising martensitic transformation temperature is required to develop HTSMAs. In this talk, phase transformation and shape memory effect of our developed alloys are presented.

CRISIS OF TRANSISTOR, AND BEYOND

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Due to the miniaturization of electronics, i.e., increasing the density of transistors in an IC chip, its computation power has been doubled every two years, following the prediction by an Intel founder Gordon E. Moore. The size of a transistor, in particular a field effect transistor (FET), has indeed shrunk a thousand fold in the last half century. The more it shrinks, the less is its power consumption, giving rise to marvellous electronic gadgets, such as a smartphone in your pocket. However, the miniaturization of FET is now faced with a crisis. If the size of FET decreases to a few nm, the number of dopants in FET becomes a few. Then, we can no more distinguish on/off currents because of Thermal noise. Among the community of condensed-matter physicists, the idea of using an electronic phase transition to FET has long been discussed. Especially, if we can tame the Mott transition, which is a drastic metal-insulator transition, for the new FET, it meets or even exceeds the predictions of the Moore's law. However, nobody has made a prototype of the Mott FET yet. One of the main challenges is a defect formation in the Mott insulator. Even though the electrochemistry of the Mott insulator is not well understood, we have proposed a unique method to suppress the defect formation, and have confirmed it is promising. In this talk, I will explain what is FET and its crisis. While introducing an idea of the advanced Mott FET, if time permitted, I will brief our recent trial to overcome the defect formation.

RECENT PROGRESS OF SiC CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR ENERGY/ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS

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SiC is one of very attractive engineering ceramics in particular for high temperature use due to high temperature strength, oxidation resistance, chemical stability and so on. SiC fiber-reinforced SiC matrix (SiC/SiC) composites basically require weak fiber/matrix interphase like pyrocarbon to avoid brittle fracture manner. The interphase material and its thickness are keys to determine material properties. However precise control of the interphase is an expensive process that results in low product yield. The purpose of this study is to develop a pseudo-ductile SiC/SiC composite using a porous SiC matrix structure without a pyrocarbon interphase and to survey its resistance against high temperature oxidation in air or steam environments by microstructural observation using FE-SEM, mechanical properties using three-point bending, weight changes using TG-DTA. The porous SiC/SiC composite without the pyrocarbon interphase was exposed at elevated temperature up to 1200 °C in air and steam environments. No apparent degradation in strength after exposure in air or stream up to 1200 °C for 10 h was observed compared to that of the as-received material. This is because the SiC/SiC composites could form protective silica layer, which showed minimal attack against air and steam below 1200 °C. On the other hands, conventional SiC/SiC composites with a PyC interphase underwent sever degradation in strength and fracture behavior after exposure in air or stream at 800 °C for 10 h due to the slight burnout of the pyrocarbon interphase. Also, many options for coating and joining of SiC/SiC composites have been investigated. Those results are provided.

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**SIZE DEPENDENT SOLUBILITY AND PHASE TRANSFORMATION
BEHAVIOR OF Sn-Cd INCLUSIONS IN Al MATRIX**

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Nanoscaled Sn-Cd alloy inclusions in Al matrix have been synthesized via rapid solidification processing route. Inclusions were found to be phase separated into two parts, one is bct tin rich and the other is hcp cadmium rich. The morphology and orientation relationship of these two phase embedded nanoscale particles have been analyzed. HRTEM and STEM-EDS analysis show that both phases exhibit size dependent solubility behavior and for particles size smaller than 18nm, single phase solid solution could only be observed. DSC studies reveal a depression in eutectic melting point of bimetallic particles. High resolution imaging indicates presence of steps across particle-matrix interface that may get annihilated during heating. During cooling, molten particles in the size range of 16-30 nm solidify as solid solution while for molten particles greater than 30 nm solidify as biphasic particle. We have also carried out a thermodynamic calculation, in order to explain the experimental observations i.e. size dependent melting behavior and complete solid solution formation in particles having size smaller than 18 nm.

**ANTICANCER EFFICACY OF DIFFERENT HEAD GROUP
CONTAINING LITHOCHOLIC ACID DERIVATIVE OF TAMOXIFEN**

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Drug membrane interactions are an important aspect of effective drug delivery and therapeutic efficacy. Amongst a large variety of strategies, drug modifications and derivatives are the most common approach adopted for achieving increased bioavailability and therapeutic outcomes. Anticancer drugs are known for their high toxicity to normal cells and drug manipulations for increasing their efficacy and selectivity to cancer cells are highly desirable. In this study, We have synthesized eight tamoxifen (Tam) -lithocholic acid (LCA) conjugates with variable cationic charged head group. Anticancer efficacy of these derivatives amphiphiles was investigated. We found that the drug permeation and therapeutic efficacy of these amphiphiles was contingent on the nature of charged head group possibly due to the strong interaction with cell membrane. Furthermore, conjugation of dimethyl amino pyridine charged head moiety made Tam effective against ER negative MDA-MB-231 cells. The study suggested that fine-tuning drug-cell membrane interactions might help in engineering of better efficacy drug delivery and therapeutic tools.

METHOXY DERIVATIVE OF WITHAFERIN A LACKS ANTICANCER POTENCY

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Withaferin A is a predominant withanolide present in the Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*). It has been shown to possess anticancer activity for a variety of human cancer cells *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Molecular mechanism of such cytotoxicity has not been not completely understood. Withanone and withaferin A were earlier shown to activate p53 tumor suppressor and oxidative stress pathways in cancer cells. Here we report the effect of a Withanone derivative on cancer cells and the proteins that have been earlier shown to be the targets of Withaferin A and Withanone. Whereas Withaferin A caused strong growth arrest/apoptosis, Methoxywithaferin A, at the equivalent doses, had no effect. Molecular analyses showed that it does not induce tumor suppressor pathways and had no effect on the oxidative signaling. The study demonstrated that the cytotoxic activity of natural withanolides is tightly controlled by their structure. Small modifications such as methylation of Withaferin A could have major impact on cell proliferation and molecular signaling

SYNTHESIS OF HIGHER MANGANESE SILICIDES TO STUDY THE ENERGY DEPENDENT SCATTERING EFFECT

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The Lead (Pb), Bismuth(Bi), and telluride based thermoelectric materials are widely used in commercial applications for harvesting waste heat, with the drawbacks of toxicity and expensive rare earth materials. The Higher Manganese Silicide (HMS) is extensively studied because of its non-toxic, environmental friendly, low cost, complex crystal structure (chimney ladder structure), and high thermal stability. Thus, HMS can be a competitive material, if its performance is improved. The energy dependent scattering effect can be effective technique to improve the performance of thermoelectric material, and therefore we tried to use it for HMS in this study. The distributed Silicon particles in HMS matrix can affect the transport properties, here the interaction of electrons with the energy band of Silicon will help in filtering high energy electrons and thus effectively increasing the Seebeck coefficient. The synthesis of MnSi_7 was done by melting high purity Mn and Si elements in induction furnace. Liquid quenching technique was used to obtain precipitates of silicon particles in HMS matrix. The bulk samples were obtained by Spark plasma sintering. The alloy composition of HMS and Silicon was precisely controlled with respect to Mn-Si binary phase diagram. The sample characterization was done by X ray diffraction, SEM and EDX. Thermal transport properties (S , σ , κ) were measured by steady state method, 4-probe method, and laser flash method, respectively. The obtained data suggest improvement of Seebeck coefficient with increasing Si concentration. The detailed results and discussion will be presented.

SUPPRESSION OF ENERGY-WASTING NON-RADIATIVE CARRIER RECOMBINATIONS IN SEMICONDUCTOR QUANTUM DOTS BY PHOTOCHEMICAL SURFACE MODIFICATION

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Colloidal semiconductor quantum dots (QDs), owing to their broad absorption and narrow emission bands, high photostability, and ability to activate multi-excitons, have become promising materials for applications such as light emitting diodes, solar energy harvesting devices, and bioimaging.¹⁻³ Despite the unique optical properties and potential applications of QDs, defects in the core and shell of QDs act as centers of nonradiative carrier recombination, which not only lower the photoluminescence (PL) quantum yield (QY) of QDs but also induce stochastic fluctuations in the PL intensity of single QDs, a phenomenon called blinking.^{3,4} Blinking is also contributed to a greater extent by the nonradiative Auger recombination in ionized QDs.^{4,5} Because of the growing interests in the applications of QDs in bioimaging and device technology, relations among surface defects, PL QY and blinking have been subjects of active investigation in the recent past. Here, we report that *in situ* surface passivation of CdSe/ZnS QDs using dithiothreitol (DTT) results in the 4-fold enhancement of PL QY of QDs.⁶ Further, single QDs treated with DTT show *in situ* blinking suppression. The PL enhancement and blinking suppression are attributed to the passivation of defects in QDs, which results in the suppression of energy-wasting nonradiative relaxations, and enables us for driving ca. 33% excess photocurrent in a photoelectrochemical cell constructed using QD-(DTT)_n as the sensitizer.

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**MOLECULARLY ENGINEERED BIONANOCAPLETS FOR
INTRACELLULAR DELIVERY: PRECISE SIZE CONTROL VIA
TEMPLATE POLYMERIZATION**

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Intracellular delivery of biomolecules (nucleic acids or proteins) is an important tool for both therapeutic and fundamental applications, however largely hindered by ineffective delivery vectors. Here we present an efficient approach for preparing tiny polymer-biomolecule complexes based on ‘template polymerization’ of molecularly engineered monomer. In the proof-of-concept study, a water-soluble Gu^+ monomer bearing two thiol termini undergoes disulfide polymerization on a siRNA/BSA-template upon oxidation to afford monodispersed polymer-siRNA/BSA complexes (siRNA/BSA-nanocaplets) of size 8 ± 2 nm. The effectiveness of this approach is demonstrated through the intracellular delivery and gene suppression by siRNA as therapeutic agent. Upon *in vitro* formulations of the siRNA-nanocaplets, siRNA is released through depolymerization of the polymer in response to a reductive cytosolic environment, and suppresses a target gene expression in living cells. *In vivo* biodistribution study in mice shows selective accumulation of the siRNA-nanocaplets in kidney after 24 h, while naked siRNA is mostly excreted.

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FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF ASHWAGANDHA LEAF EXTRACT FOR ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

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Ashwagandha leaves have been shown to possess anticancer activities. Withanolide constituents present in the alcoholic extract of leaves, such as withanone and withaferin A, kill cancer cells by mechanisms involving apoptosis and growth arrest. Whereas withanone causes selective cancer cell killing, withaferin A, in high dose, was found to be cytotoxic to normal cells in *in vitro* assays. Withaferin A in combination with withanone was less toxic to normal cells and synergistically enhanced the anti-migration effect on cancer cells. We also prepared water extract of leaves and found that it was also toxic to cancer cells. The anticancer activity in the water extract was assigned to its active compound, triethylene glycol (TEG), as identified by chemical characterization including HPLC and NMR. Whereas the alcoholic extract was seen to activate p53 pathway, the water extract caused activation of pRb protein in cancer cells. These results predicted the using herb as such or extracts that contain both water and alcohol soluble components for cancer treatment.

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**PROSTAGLANDIN D₂ IS CRUCIAL FOR SEIZURE
SUPPRESSION AND POSTICTAL SLEEP**

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Epilepsy is a neurological disorder with the occurrence of seizures, which are often accompanied by sleep. Prostaglandin (PG) D₂ is produced by hematopoietic or lipocalin-type PGD synthase (H- or L-PGDS) and involved in the regulation of physiological sleep. Here, we show that H-PGDS, L/H-PGDS or DP₁ receptor (DP₁R) KO mice exhibited more intense pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)- induced seizures in terms of latency of seizure onset, duration of generalized tonic-clonic seizures, and number of seizure spikes. Seizures significantly increased the PGD₂ content of the brain in wild-type mice. This PTZ-induced increase in PGD₂ was attenuated in the brains of L- or H-PGDS KO and abolished in L/H-PGDS KO mice. Postictal non-rapid eye movement sleep was observed in the wild-type and H-PGDS or DP₂R KO, but not in the L-, L/H-PGDS or DP₁R KO, mice. These findings demonstrate that PGD₂ produced by H-PGDS and acting on DP₁R is essential for seizure suppression and that the L-PGDS/PGD₂/DP₁R system regulates sleep that follows seizures.

CELL STRESS MARKER PROTEIN-CARF

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CARF, Collaborator of ARF (Alternate Reading Frame) is an ARF-inducing protein that activates ARF-p53 pathway. Overexpression of CARF causes growth arrest in cancer cells, its knockdown triggers apoptosis, suggesting that it is an essential protein for cell survival. Molecular analyses of CARF functions revealed that it is upregulated during normal ageing process and is induced in response to a variety of drugs that cause premature aging. Senescence induced by oncogenic RAS and deprotection of telomeres also showed upregulation of CARF at the transcriptional as well as translational levels. Investigations on the molecular mechanism of the role of CARF in this phenomena demonstrated that CARF is an essential factor in DNA damage response signaling. It works upstream of p53 to cause growth arrest and regulates cell proliferation fates by feed-forward and feedback signaling of DNA damage and growth regulatory proteins.

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LONG TERM EFFECT OF NUTRIENTS - NITROGEN - GROUNDWATER ANALYSIS IN A GLOBAL-SCALE BY USING LSM- MATSIRO- NCM

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Groundwater is emerging as a critical issue and plays an important role in the sustainable use of water resource management. To understand the sustainable water management in a globalized world, it is necessary to estimate the groundwater discharge and the analysis is integrated into a LSMs, the Minimal Advanced Treatments of Surface Integration and Runoff (MATSIRO) (Takata et al., 2003). Due to anthropogenic climatic change, groundwater recharge is and will be changing as both the total runoff and the partitioning of total runoff into surface and fast sub-surface flow and groundwater recharge is altered. However, total runoff as well as groundwater recharge will mainly change with the change in precipitation. And also precipitation changes during the major recharge season which is most relevant (Döll and Flörke, 2005). The Nitrogen Cycle Model (NCM) is developed to consider the mass balance of nitrogen in the natural ecosystem integrated with the carbon cycle in vegetation and organic soil (Yang et al., 2009). The ecosystem was divided into an atmospheric, vegetation and soil reservoir. The NCM consists in biological processes which depend on the variety of the environmental factors. The effect on surface energy balance is, however, controlled by climate, soil, and vegetation conditions. The nitrate leaching is strongly related to soil water content, soil texture, and NO_3^- concentration. Under current climatic conditions and excess use of nitrate concentrations of groundwater in agricultural purposes are already a serious problem with many groundwater abstractions containing nitrate concentration which exceed the agricultural purposes limit.

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ATOMISTIC MODELLING TO UNDERSTAND, DESCRIBE, AND DESIGN ABSORBER MATERIALS FOR THIN-FILM SOLAR CELL APPLICATIONS

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Current thin-film solar cells photovoltaic (PV) technologies are dominating with materials like CdTe, Cu(Ga,In)Se₂ and Cu₂ZnSnS₄. However, the price volatility issues (In, Ga), supply issues (In, Te), and environmental issues (Cd) are of great concern in these materials for future clean and efficient technology. To overcome these issues, there has been huge interest in developing materials that contain abundant, eco-friendly, and low-cost elements. Therefore in this study, we discussed the importance of indium-free Cu_x(Sb,Bi)_y(S,Se)_z system and AB₂ compounds (A= Sr, Ba; B= Si, Ge) which contain inexpensive and earth abundant elements, for solar cell applications. Employing first-principles modeling within the density function theory, we analyze the structural, electronic and optical properties and find that the fundamental band gap energies are in the region of 0.9–1.8 eV, which is suitable for solar cell applications [2-5]. Furthermore, a lower energy dispersion

of the conduction band (CB), which results in a flat shape of the CB minimum, implies a large optical absorption [2-5]. In fact, our calculations reveal that the photoabsorption of these compounds is stronger than other PV materials like Si or CuInSe₂ (Fig. 1) [5]. Thereby, these indium-free Cu_x(Sb,Bi)_y(S,Se)_z system and AB₂ compounds possess a great potential as suitable light absorber materials for application in future thin-film solar cell clean technologies

Fig.1 Absorption coefficients $\alpha(\omega)$

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SYNTHESIS OF BIOTIN-SUGAR CONJUGATE AS AN ATTRACTIVE BIOPROBE (III)

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Bio-probes are functional molecules or devices that provide information about biological systems. Biotin (244.31 Da) is known as a vitamin B7 and use as a bioprobe for avidin or streptavidin. Because of high affinity between biotin and avidin, synthetic assembly of the biotin and other bioactive compounds (primary amines, sulfhydryls, carboxyls and carbohydrates) are of great interest in biochemical and biomedical research fields in order to evaluate activities of the bioactive compounds. In this research *N*-acetyl-D-glucosamine (GlcNAc) is used as a target carbohydrate. The carboxyl group of biotin is the site of attachment of the molecule and in first few steps we introduced amino containing linker to the particular carbohydrate and after completion of those steps we made an interaction between carboxyl group of biotin with amino group linker attached with sugar through an amide bond in the presence of DMT-MM coupling reagent¹). After getting the target compound, binding of biotin-GlcNAc conjugate with avidin or streptavidin takes place. Tryptophan may occur in a residual form after biotin protein binding and the binding of biotin can be blocked by oxidation of any of several tryptophan residues. To check the binding affinity of biotin conjugate with WGA (Wheat Germ Agglutinin) we use fluorometric assay by means of specific excitation of tryptophan at λ_{ex} 295 nm. In addition, sizes of the complexes are also measured by light scattering method. We are now aiming to purify the target compound and complete chemical analysis of targeted compound.

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PERFECT CONGRUENCE OF THE ASSAY RESULTS PERFORMED BY THE AMES TEST AND THE GPMA METHOD

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The mutagenicity of chemicals has been of great concern due to the strong correlation between mutagenicity and cancer. Since the invention of the Ames test, not a few of mutagenicity detection assays have been developed. Among them, a unique mutation assay termed as genome profiling-based mutation assay (GPMA), which depends on the direct measure of DNA mutation, was further developed to the mammalian cell dependent one (originally bacterial-dependent) in this study. First, the high sensitivity (10 ppb level) of the original GPMA was confirmed using mutagenic chemicals (53 species). The agreement between the Ames test and bacterial cell-based GPMA (GPMA-b) in the discrimination ability of mutagens was 98% (115 out of 117), which may be further improved by the refinement of the GPMA method. Then, owing to the high sensitivity, the novel mammalian cell dependent one (GPMA-m) was devised. The experimental system could be made up of 7 days culture of murine 3T3 cells (5 generations) at 100 ppb of each test chemical, which was a simple extension of GPMA-b only by changing the experimental organism. For those samples tested (20 species), the congruence was perfect between the assay results obtained by the Ames test and GPMA-m. There was relatively high correlations ($r = 0.78$) between the quantitative results measured by GPMA-b and GPMA-m. This study opened the way to employ diversities of mammalian cells for the mutagenicity test. As a result, the more exact and versatile detection of cancer-causing chemicals will become possible.

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DEVELOPMENT OF NEW HIGH TEMPERATURE TITANIUM ALLOY WITH IMPROVED PROPERTIES BY NITRIDE ADDITION

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Titanium alloys are widely used in aerospace applications because of their superior properties like light weight, high strength, good high temperature strength, corrosion resistance, superior fatigue and creep properties. In jet engines Ti alloys are used as compressor discs and blades; however the maximum temperature is limited to 600°C. For the component subjected to temperature above 600°C, heavy and expensive Ni based super alloys are being used. It would be very useful, if a new Ti alloys with improved mechanical properties, that can be usable in the temperature range above 600°C has been developed. Alloying is one of the fundamental methods to improve the mechanical properties of metals. In the present study, the effect of nitride addition on room temperature and high temperature mechanical properties of near alpha Ti alloy has been investigated. The compression test results showed that nitride addition significantly improves both the room temperature and high temperature compressive yielding strength. The nitrogen combined with Ti and form TiN compound. TiN is hard and act as a precipitation strengthener that improves the room temperature and high temperature mechanical properties. However the improvement in strength is accompanied by loss in ductility. The alloy composition is optimized to obtain maximum improvement in strength without a loss in ductility. The results obtained were explained based on the microstructural examination using electron microscopes and mechanical property evaluation using compression tests.

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF TI-MO ALLOYS WITH ELEMENTAL SEGREGATION

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Due to the high specific strength, high corrosion resistance and good biocompatibility, β -Titanium alloys are widely used in numerous application fields from aerospace to biomedical materials. The structural materials with superior combination of mechanical properties are always the researchers trying to develop. With a high amount of molybdenum as an effective β -phase stabilizer in metastable Ti-Mo alloys, swirly segregation pattern forms named as 'van Gogh's Sky' (VGS) structure. Our previous investigation showed that the VGS structure has the potential to improve the balance of tensile properties [1]. The objective of the present study is to characterize the deformation mechanism of tensile behavior in Ti-Mo alloy with elemental segregation. Solution treated Ti-12Mo alloy with segregation structure were prepared. Room temperature tensile tests were carried out at strain rates ranging from 3×10^{-1} to 3×10^{-4} s⁻¹ with round bar sample. XRD and SEM with EDS and EBSD analysis were used. Based on the true stress-strain curves after tensile tests at various strain rates the increasing strain rate led to an increase in the yield strength with sacrifice of the total elongation and the work hardening rate. Meanwhile α'' martensite was identified by XRD analysis and $\{332\} \langle 113 \rangle$ twinning was observed by EBSD in the sample after tensile fracture. Existence of combined deformation modes including dislocation slip, $\{332\} \langle 113 \rangle$ twinning and stress-induced martensitic transformation was confirmed in the Ti-12Mo alloy with VGS structure.

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PHYTOCHEMICALS WITH ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

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Cancer is a complicated and multifactorial disease. It often requires a combinational therapy to target more than a few signaling pathways that are activated in cancer cells. In this viewpoint, we investigated the anticancer activities of some phytochemicals (withaferin A, triethylene glycol and its derivatives, caffeic acid phenethyl ester and embelin) in comparison with conventional clinically accepted anticancer drugs, (adriamycin and 5-Fluorouracil) using cultured bone cancer (U2OS) cells. We found that the phytochemicals, withaferin A, triethylene glycol and its derivatives were cytotoxic at low doses as compared to caffeic acid phenethyl ester and embelin. Triethylene glycol derivatives were highly cytotoxic and triggered apoptosis. Biochemical and immunostaining analyses for (i) p53, a major DNA damage response and growth arrest mediating protein, (ii) ezrin, a cytoskeleton protein that plays a key role in cell surface structure, adhesion and motility and (iii) stress chaperone mortalin that plays role in mitochondrial functions, protection against oxidative stress and deregulation of apoptosis were performed. We found increase in p53, although to a variable extent, with most of the phytochemicals indicating activation of DNA damage and growth arrest signaling. Phytochemicals, such as withaferin A, triethylene glycol, caffeic acid phenethyl ester and embelin resulted in decreased expression of ezrin and mortalin suggesting that anticancer potential either by themselves or in conjunction with conventional drugs.

**OXIDATIVE STRESS TO LUNG CANCER CELLS BY ASHWAGANDHA
LEAF EXTRACT AND ITS ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS**

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Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) is a most popular herb used in Ayurveda, Indian traditional home medicine system. It is also called as Queen of Ayurveda. The main active constituents of Ashwagandha are alkaloids and steroidal lactones, commonly known as withanolides and have been shown to possess anticancer activity. Whereas withanolides, such as withanone and withaferin A are rich in the alcoholic extracts of Ashwagandha, water extract was shown to contain Triethylene glycol (TEG) that caused growth arrest or apoptosis of human cancer cells. Molecular studies have revealed that these compounds may cause induction of oxidative stress, activation of tumor suppressor proteins and alterations in cytoskeleton elements. We have investigated the molecular mechanism of the cytotoxicity of withaferin A and TEG in human cancer cells. We found that whereas high doses of withaferin A and TEG caused apoptosis, their low doses led to growth arrest of cancer cells, and were relatively safe for normal cells. We found that such selective toxicity of low doses of withaferin A and TEG was mediated by decrease in the expression level of a stress regulatory proteins including mortalin, Nrf2 and NFκB, and was marked by induction of oxidative stress.

INFLUENCE OF Cu CONTENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SEVERELY DEFORMED 7000 ALUMINUM ALLOYS

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Recently, techniques of severe plastic deformation (SPD) such as high pressure torsion (HPT) have attracted attention as a promising method to improve materials properties without changing their chemical composition. 7000 Aluminum alloys (Al-Zn-Mg-(Cu)) are well known structural materials that contain high specific strength (220 kN · m /kg). In this study, we focus on the influence of Cu content on the mechanical properties of severely plastically deformed 7000 Aluminum alloys. Al-2.5Zn-2.5Mg (0 Cu) (at%), Al-2.5Zn-2.5Mg-0.5Cu (0.5 Cu), Al-2.5Zn-2.5Mg-1.0Cu (1.0 Cu) were processed by HPT. We have carried out micro Vickers hardness test and tensile testing to investigate the mechanical properties such as hardness and tensile strength. Microstructure characterization was performed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). HPT processing after 10 turns led to a grain refinement to 100-200 nm. At this strain level, the maximum micro Vickers hardness was 198 Hv for the 0 Cu alloy, 241 Hv for the 0.5 Cu alloy and 273 Hv for the 1.0 Cu. TEM observations revealed the precipitation of η' phase ($MgZn_2$) during HPT processing. The observed hardness increase can be attributed to grain refinement, high dislocation density and precipitation hardening. We observed a decrease in the ductility after HPT processing. For instance, after 10 HPT turns, the total elongation of the 1.0 Cu alloy decreased approximately 40 %.

EMBELIN INHIBITS TNF- α CONVERTING ENZYME (TACE) AND CANCER CELL MIGRATION

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Embelin, a quinone derivative present in fruits of *Embelia ribes* (Myrsinaceae). It is known as false black pepper in English, Vidanga in Sanskrit. It has been known for a variety of therapeutic activities including anthelmintic, analgesic, anti-diabetic, anti-convulsant and anti-inflammation and anti-tumor. Inflammation signaling is closely linked with tumorigenesis. It is an immunological response to external harmful stimuli and is regulated by an endogenous pro-inflammatory cytokine, tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) that has been implicated in a variety of human pathologies including cancer. TNF- α is synthesized as a membrane anchored protein (pro-TNF α); the soluble component of pro-TNF α is then released into the extracellular space by the action of a protease called TNF- α converting enzyme (TACE). TACE has, hence, been proposed as a therapeutic target for inflammation and cancer. In the present study, we report that embelin inhibits TACE. We demonstrate that embelin treated human breast cancer cells have reduced TACE and show inhibition in growth and cancer properties including colony forming efficacy, migration and invasion that were seen to be mediated by down regulation of MMP-2, MMP-9, VEGF and hnRNP-K.

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**BIOINSPIRED ADHESIVE POLYMER/MACROMOLECULES AS
MULTIFUNCTIONAL SURFACE COATINGS**

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Structural metals/alloys are inevitable part of our daily life and numerous industrial applications. One key issue of using such materials is to maintain their structural/functional integrity and appearance from external hazards. There are several methods such as chromate passivation, electrochemical plating, anodizing, and coatings to overcome these shortcomings. Generally, in those cases a protection layer forms on the metal surface, which consists of several tens to hundreds of μm in thickness. On the other hand, during last few decades a huge demand has emerged in materials science/technology for compact size, weight and sophisticated devices/tools. These trends have led to a significant advance in the field of nano-materials/technology, resulting in new innovations with structural metals/alloys. Considering reduced metal backbone dimensions and weight, protection layer has to be more sophisticated and thin, possibly below sub-micron level, with adequate performance and versatility. Therefore, it is need of hour to develop ultra-thin, versatile, eco-friendly, and easy coating technique for state-of-the-art structural architectures. At present, we demonstrate an efficient and versatile coatings technique inspired by an underwater bio-adhesion mechanism. Many marine organisms survive under harsh deep sea condition and they do it by a unique adhesive foot, which contains mainly catechol and amine units. By mimicking this natural phenomenon, we prepared a wide-range of synthetic polymers and macromolecules for practical applications in diverse fields including anticorrosion, antifouling, adhesive, and smart coatings of metals/alloys. Our study revealed that a simple combination of anchoring catechol moieties and hydrophobic alkyl chains led to an efficient and versatile coating method.

ASHWAGANDHA FOR PROTECTION AGAINST THE OXIDATIVE STRESS AND PARAQUAT-INDUCED PARKINSON

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Ashwagandha has been known for its memory enhancement and stress protector in Ayurveda. In the present study, we have investigated the neuroprotective potential of Ashwagandha leaf and root extracts, against oxidative stress in particular, using *in vitro* cell culture-based assays and *in vivo* mouse model. We found that the extracts and the purified component, withanone, when used at low dose, protected the glial and neuronal cells from oxidative as well as glutamate insult, and induced their differentiation *per se* in *in vitro* assays. Withaferin A (in equivalent doses), on the other hand, was toxic to cells and did not offer protection against stress. Furthermore, the extracts and the active components, in combination were highly potent, endorsing Therapeutic merit of the combinational approach. In *in vivo* paraquat (PQ)-induced Parkinson disease (PD) mouse model, pre-treatment with Ashwagandha extract reduced the toxicity of PQ on brain as determined by behavioral, biochemical, molecular and imaging assays. We found that Ashwagandha extract (low doses)-treated cells in *in vitro* and *in vivo* were protected against oxidative stress-induced apoptosis. Taken together, we conclude that Ashwagandha extracts and phytochemicals, withanone in particular, protect against oxidative stress and its related pathologies.

MORTALIN LOCALIZES TO THE NUCLEUS AND CONTRIBUTES TO CANCER CELL PROPERTIES

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Mortalin is a member of Hsp70 family of stress chaperons. It plays indispensable role in the mitochondrial functions, oxidative stress response, intracellular transport, chaperonization, and is frequently enriched in cancer cells. It is found in various subcellular sites including mitochondria, plasma membrane, endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and cytosol. We discovered that the malignantly transformed cells have more mortalin in the nucleus than the normal cells. To delineate the functional significance of nuclear mortalin, we generated its mutant that lacked the mitochondrial targeting N-terminal 41 amino acids signal peptide sequence. The mutant (mot-N) was largely localized in nucleus. Functional characterization of mot-N showed that it efficiently protects cancer cells against endogenous and exogenous oxidative stress. Furthermore, compared to the full-length mortalin (mot-F), mot-N derivatives showed increased malignant properties including faster growth, motility and tumor forming capacity both in *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. We demonstrate that nuclear mortalin promotes carcinogenesis and cancer cell metastasis by (i) inactivation of tumor suppressor protein p53 functions and (ii) interaction and functional activation of telomerase and heterogeneous ribonucleoprotein-K (hnRNP-K) proteins. It may serve as a marker for aggressive cancers. Information obtained from this study is important for developing mortalin-based anticancer treatment.

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SIMPLIFIED COLLAPSE ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURES USING THE EXTENDED DISTINCT ELEMENT METHOD WITH FINITE ELEMENT MAPPING

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Collapse analysis of buildings is invaluable in the field of Urban Disaster Reduction. There exists various scientific methods for collapse analysis, however, these methods are usually complicated and time consuming to be used in actual practice. There is a need for a numerical tool which is simple, accurate and computationally less expensive for practical seismic vulnerability assessment of buildings. The Extended Distinct Element Method was observed to be a simple as well as an efficient tool for modelling collapse of structures. But it has some limitations, namely, requirement of small time increment for stability and accuracy, lack of a proper solid mechanics theory for spring constants derivation, and, no consideration of the Poisson's effect. A study is carried out in overcoming these limitations by (i) using an implicit numerical scheme from elastic till nonlinear phase and an explicit scheme during collision/collapse phase, thereby enabling the usage of a larger time increment during the initial phase, hence reducing the computation time, and, (ii) using spring constants for the Distinct Element assembly, obtained from the Finite Element Mapping for Spring Network Representation of Mechanics of Solids, which essentially provides a rigorous method of spring constants derivation for 2D/3D elastic media. Simulations for each phase viz. linear, non-linear, and collapse are performed and results are compared with past experimental data and other numerical simulation results. This study presents a new simplified method of analysis to simulate the building behavior during an earthquake, from elastic state to a state of complete collapse.

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF TRUSS BRIDGES USING VIBRATION MEASUREMENT

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In assessing the condition and performance of existing civil engineering infrastructure, an effective maintenance technique with high reliability is needed to be established. As a compliment to direct visual inspection, vibration based damage detection has been seen as a promising technique for structural health monitoring (SHM). The most efficient vibration based SHM approach consists of four different stages: (1) Optimal sensor placement; (2) System identification; (3) Finite element model updating and (4) Damage detection. The first step is the optimal sensor placement where the sensors must be placed judiciously in order to obtain sufficient information about dynamic behaviour of a large structural system with limited number of sensors. In the second step, the modal parameters are identified from measured vibration data by applying some reliable and efficient system identification techniques. The model updating is then carried out in the third step utilizing extracted modal parameters to minimize the discrepancies between finite element model and actual structure. In this research work Bayesian based probabilistic approach is considered for finite element model updating which has many advantages compared to other conventional methods. The last step is the diagnosis of damage by comparing undamaged and possibly damaged structures. In this study, Mogami steel truss bridge is considered for the demonstration of various methods of SHM.

DEVELOPMENT OF A NOVEL POWDER METALLURGY ROUTE TO FABRICATE BIOMEDICAL BETA-TITANIUM ALLOYS

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In recent years, Ti-Nb based alloys have attracted significant interest as a promising material for biomedical applications, such as body implants. These Ti-Nb-based alloys are considered suitable for such biomedical applications due to their unique combination of physical and chemical properties, i.e. low young modulus, comparable to that of the human bone, coupled with excellent corrosion resistance and bio-compatibility. However, preparing fine-grained Ti-Nb-alloys, with high strength and retained low young modulus, via conventional ingot metallurgy processing approach has been an important and critical issue due to the difficulties associated with Thermo-mechanical treatment of these alloys at elevated temperature. Powder metallurgy is considered an efficient and attractive method to prepare fine-grained alloys with controlled/tailored microstructure. In the present work, a new powder metallurgy route has been developed to fabricate fine-grained beta Ti-Nb-based alloys from elemental powders. The proposed route involved mechanical milling (MM) of TiH₂ and elemental Nb powder mixture followed by their consolidation. The MM of blended powders was carried out for different period of time using planetary ball mill. Subsequently, the MM powder was consolidated by Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS). In the present work, microstructural evolution at every stage of processing of Ti-40 wt%Nb is presented and discussed. Moreover, the effect of milling time and SPS temperature on the microstructure of the sintered binary Ti-40Nb alloy compacts were also evaluated, and the results related to this aspect are also presented and discussed.

STUDY ON CENTRIFUGAL FORCES BASED PARTICLE. TRAPPING IN MICRO CHAMBER AT LOWER REYNOLDS NUMBER

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Important applications of microfluidic in cell biology is sorting, trapping, sampling and analysis of cells. Among these sorting and trapping of cells are basic and important tasks to perform. Many modern method of cell separation techniques have been reported but in medical as well as biological field density based separation is in demand for purification of cells. This paper reports circular trajectory of micro particle inside trapping chamber at relatively lower Reynolds number ($Re = 100$) as compared to previous trapping of particles by vortex trajectory at relatively higher Reynolds number [1]. Density based sorting [2] of samples is often crucial step for biological and chemical preparations. We examined particle behavior in microchip by changing flow rates and diameter of trapping chamber. Figure 1 shows that at 1000 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ and 1mm trapping chamber curved trajectory of particle observed at lower Reynolds number ($Re = 100$) but no loop trajectory was observed. It is because of the fact that channel and trapping chamber are at same height which hindered the trajectory of the particles. Further we fabricated microchip with increased height of trapping chamber in order to increase retention time of particles. Experimental results showed that high density silica particle ($d \sim 2.5\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$) revolved around periphery of chamber with circular motion while lower density polystyrene particle ($d \sim 1.09\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$) revolved around center of the chamber. This result clearly demonstrated the effect of centrifugal force on the trajectory of same sized particle having different densities.

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IMPLICATIONS OF TARGETING TRANSCRIPTIONAL FACTOR PPAR GAMMA FOR BREAST CANCER THERAPEUTICS

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The peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) are ligand activated transcriptional factors, belonging to the nuclear receptor superfamily, that plays a vital role in regulation of expression of genes involved in cell differentiation, proliferation organogenesis, inflammation, carbohydrate and lipid. PPAR γ ligands have been reported as a new and potentially efficacious treatment of cancer, inflammation, diabetes, obesity, AD, and schizophrenia. In cancer, PPAR γ is overexpressed depicting its critical role in cancer cell survival, which has been confirmed by *in vitro* anti cancer activity of PPAR γ ligands against a wide variety of neoplastic cells. Recent withdrawal of PPAR γ agonists - Thiazolidinediones (TZDs) (e.g. - troglitazone (Rezulin), rosiglitazone (Avandia), and pioglitazone (Actos)) highlights the lack of understanding of the molecular basis of these drugs, their off-target effects which further underscores the complexity of PPAR γ signaling mechanisms. Understanding the molecular signaling pathways that link tumor biology to the staggering array of genes and pathologies is of paramount medical and scientific importance. In this study we briefly discuss about function and role of PPAR γ in cancer biology, it's transcriptional targets and it's emergence as a promising therapeutic target in breast cancer. These investigations will help us in understanding the molecular mechanisms by which PPAR γ regulates cancer cell proliferation and opens a new direction for development of it's ligands in human breast cancer therapeutics.

THE RELATIVE INFLUENCES OF ENSO CONVENTIONAL, ENSO MODOKI AND INDIAN OCEAN DIPOLE ON MINDANAO AND NORTHEASTERN BORNEO PRECIPITATION ANOMALY

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Many had thought that El Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO), Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD), and El Nino Modoki (EM) are influencing the precipitation in Mindanao and Northeastern Borneo. However, no study was done to identify the real impact of these three climate phenomena on the precipitation of this area. Based on the situation above, this study intends to investigate the influence of ENSO, IOD and EM to Mindanao and Northeastern Borneo precipitation. Besides that, we are investigating factor other than those dominant climate phenomena that affect the precipitation in the study region. For this study, we used APHRODITE (observation precipitation data) as our primary precipitation data. For analysis, we used 850hPa wind data (JRA-55), sea level pressure data (SLP; JRA-55) and sea surface temperature data (SST; HadISST) from 1961 to 2007. Correlation, partial correlation and composite analyses are used as the method for this study. We discovered that ENSO during December-February (DJF), March-May and September-November (SON) influence the precipitation in the study region. Further analysis indicated that EM during DJF and SON influences precipitation of those regions. However, IOD influence is not significant in any season. It is also discovered that the precipitation in the region is greatly affected by the regional monsoon winds of East Asian Winter Monsoon during DJF. In addition, the winter monsoon rainfall is influenced by the winds that are in turn associated with the variations in Siberian High. Further analysis will be done to understand the links among them (regional monsoon winds and SLP).

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POTENTIAL OF TRIETHYLENE GLYCOL DERIVATIVES AS DRUGS FOR CANCER THERAPY

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Triethylene glycol (TEG) was shown to be present in the leaf extract of Ashwagandha and caused cancer cell killing by activation of p53 and pRB tumor suppressor pathways. In *in vivo* nude mice tumor formation and metastasis assays, it caused tumor suppression and reduction in lung metastasis of tumor cells injected into the tail vein. In view of these findings, we investigated effect of three derivatives of TEG (Triethylene glycol monobutyl ether- TriEGmbE, Tetraethylene glycol dimethacrylate- TetEGdma) and Triethylene glycol dimethacrylate- TriEGdMA) on cancer cell growth and migration. We report that TetEGdma and TriEGdMA kill human cancer cells with high efficacy in comparison to the several other phytochemicals and conventional anticancer drugs. We found that they target mutant p53 and hnRNP-K proteins that play important role in carcinogenesis and metastasis suggesting that these may be good candidates cancer therapy.

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